

Multi-Narrative Storytelling, Hypnotism of Aquinas' Realism and *Intentio*—Rediscovering Fra Angelico's *the Mocking of Christ*

Abstract: This article initially examines three stages of Christ being mocked in the Gospels and compares the scriptural description with Fra Angelico's *the Mocking of Christ* and two manuscripts of *Speculum Humanae Salvationis*. The reason for Christ wearing a raiment in white rather than in purple or velvet as described by the Gospels may imply the Savior's dying and resurrection in resemblance to the absterging process of baptism. In wake of a preliminary hypothesis that the fresco may have been embedded in multiple biblical narratives, new evidence of bycocket characteristic of Herod's costume as can be seen on the third panel of the Passion Cope from Waterford can possibly narrow down the scope of its reference text to the Luke. With the fresco scripturally and iconographically analyzed, those alarming disembodied hands lead to the last section of philosophical meditation. Thomas Aquinas's critical approach towards platonic idea accounts for the reason why those hands (palms) are solely represented and his epistemic theories about *intentio* as well as Angelico's distinctive practice of *Dissemblance* and *Figura* also endow a new vision to interpret the myths beneath those off-body hands that besiege Christ.

Keywords: Mocking of Christ; Baptism; Thomas Aquinas; Realism; Intentionality; Dissemblance; *Figura*

The Mocking of Christ (1440) is one of the most mythical and iconic frescoes painted by Fra Angelico for the 7th Cell of the Convent of San Marco in Florence (Fig. 1). Upon the fresco, Jesus Christ, in white garment, sits on a scarlet square base with a crown of thorns, holding a rod in his right hand and an orb in the other. His softly dropped eyes are veiled by a white gauze that emits the reddish color and lustre of his face. Intriguingly, his scoffers except for the man with a hat on the left are solely embodied

with off-body hands.

Fig. 1. Fra Angelico, *The Mocking of Christ, with the Virgin and Saint Dominic*, fresco, c. 1439-1443, Cell 7, Convent of San Marco, Florence.

1. RECONNECTING THE FRESCO WITH THE BIBLES AND ITS PICTORIAL CONTEMPORARIES

According to the record of Matthew, Luke and Mark in *the Holy Bibles*, the umbrella event of *The Mocking of Christ* can be chopped up into three subplots which though forming “a unity of action of the mocking”, have contradictory statements due to their sources. At the first stage of the Christ being mocked, Matthew, Luke and Mark reach an unanimity in describing the action of the high priest and other offenders as “mock”

and “smote”, whilst both Matthew and Mark further highlight the way those aggressors insult the Christ—they spit on him, of which Luke says nothing, unexpectedly¹. As to the Christ’s outfit, the Matthew does not drop any hints, while the Luke mentions the Christ being blindfolded and the Mark his face being covered. Hence the bibles are partially at odds with each other in how the Christ is molested and affronted at the first stage of the mocking. The next stage witnesses an enormous disparity in narratives. Both Matthew and Mark stress the Christ’s dressing—himself stripped with a purple or scarlet robe, imposed to wear a crown of thorns and thrust with a reed, so as to “mimic” the King of the Jews for the sake of being made fun of, where violent acts like “spit”, “smote” and “mock” reoccur². Nevertheless, Luke withdraws this corresponding story to the minimum of “characters”, “locations (on the change)” and “events” in a far more economical way³. So far, in wake of two analyzed stages of the mocking, it seems that the pictorial elements of Fra Angelico’s *The Mocking of Christ* such as the blindfold and thorny crown have been literally fulfilled to a sufficient extent. But still, a) of which stage(s) of mocking is the image representative, along with b) the reason why other pictorial elements are deviated from those accounts of the Bibles remain perplexing, therefore, a retrospection to other images prior to or contemporaneous with Angelico’s fresco is entailed to examine the latter.

The screening criteria lie in the coloring of garment which may help images take sides. While many manuscript illustrations have pigmented Christ’s garments as scarlet or purple, two images that display Christ in white eventually came into sight: collected by the Bibliothèque nationale de France and the University of Cambridge, they appear in manuscripts of *Speculum Humanae Salvationis*, in which the visual realizations of the

¹ See *The Holy Bible, Containing the Old Testament and the New: Newly Translated Out of the Original Tongues, and with the Former Translations Diligently Compared and Revised. By His Majesties Special Command. Appointed to be Read in Churches.* London: John Baskett and the Assigns of Henry Hills, deceas'd, 1728. Chap. xxvi-67, Chap. xxii-63 and Chap. xiv-61.

² *Ibid.*, see Chap. xxvii-29, and Chap. xv-17.

³ *Ibid.*, see Chap. xxiii-11.

mocking have shown endeavor in adaptation from the Latin text that prevailed in late medieval Europe in the form of a lengthy poem of the popular genre of *specula*. According to the text of the poem, the mocking of Christ follows the biblical narrative of redemption, able to be categorized into three phases: i.) Mocking of Christ; ii.) Christ crowned with the crown of thorns and mocked; iii.) Longinus piercing Christ's side and Jews mocking him. Of the first phase, the offenders veil Christ's eyes with a certain covering and taint his face with much spit. He gets slapped when being asked to predict and describe who is the person that strikes him⁴. The text also provides a detail that does not come up in the Bibles—His hands which have at the beginning molded heaven and earth are now tied up⁵. What follows is the second phase when the evil offenders deem the suffering of Christ to be far from enough and thus invent a new game of punishments that package Christ as a king for mockery. They impose a coverlet resembling a scarlet or purple—the royal badge on him, put a thorny crown in place of golden crown on his head, and eventually press a reed into his hand in imitation of holding a golden scepter⁶. Therefore, it is only at the second phase that the crown of thorns and reed show up. In MS Latin 511 preserved by the Bibliothèque nationale de France, the illustration placed above the text of the first phase depicts Christ standing in the midst of kooky offenders, his unbound hands folding in front of his chests and his eyes being unveiled at all, which go astray from the textual denotation (fig. 2). In comparison, another image of the first-phase mocking which comes from MS Add. 6447 preserved by the University of Cambridge has already shown some qualities of compliance to the text as Christ becomes blindfolded, yet the humiliating acts of “spit”, “slap” and “hands bound” are not visualized either (fig. 3). Additionally, the image of Christ who wears a thorny crown with a reed in hand has transcended the “to-do list” of the first phase of mocking, in many ways resembling the image of the second phase

⁴ Ludolf, von Sachsen, approximately 1300-1377 or 1378, supposed author; Lutz, Jules, [from old catalog] ed; Perdrizet, Paul, 1870- [from old catalog] joint ed; Miélot, Jean, active 15th century, tr; Munich. K. Hof- und staatsbibliothek. Mss. (Cod. lat. Monac. 146) [from old catalog], *Speculum Humanae Salvationis*, Mülhausen, Buchdr. E. Meininger, 1907, p. 40.

⁵ *Ibid.*

⁶ *Ibid.*, p. 44.

of mocking in MS Latin 511, which shows the blindfolded Christ as sitting on an exquisitely engraved lithic base, with blood being shed from the thorny crown and a reed of exaggerated size being thrust in his hand (Fig. 4). The image of the second phase of mocking in MS Add. 6447 displays Christ, whose eyes are kept open and whose head dons a thorny crown, sitting on a ladder in a casual pose with a reed in hand. Offenders who constantly badger him are making insulting gestures or raising palms to smote him, whose imagery seems to retrogress to match with the narratives of the first phase (Fig. 5). From the above analysis that an acclaimed image of one phase may encompass elements of the other, a preliminary conclusion could be drawn that the medieval artisans may not have realized the clear-cut boundary of different phases of mocking and consequently contributed to a mix or missing of the elements. Further, it could be deduced that Angelico's *The Mocking of Christ*, owing to the synchronicity of impertinent "spit" and "slap" with the cynical "blindfold" and "crown of thorns", is a mixed-blood of both phases of mocking. In addition, Christ's holding a crystal orb in hand is not straightforwardly described in the text but rather euphemistically implied by "cuius manus in principio coelum et terram plasmaverunt"⁷, thus the orb may be symbolic of "terram".

⁷ Ludolf, von Sachsen, approximately 1300-1377 or 1378, supposed author; Lutz, Jules, [from old catalog] ed; Perdrizet, Paul, 1870- [from old catalog] joint ed; Miélot, Jean, active 15th century, tr; Munich. K. Hof- und staatsbibliothek. Mss. (Cod. lat. Monac. 146) [from old catalog], *Speculum Humanae Salvationis*, Mülhausen, Buchdr. E. Meininger, 1907, p. 40.

Phase 1:
Mocking
of Christ

Fig. 2. Illustration for Vincent of Beauvais's *Speculum Humanae Salvationis*, MS Latin 511 (19v), parchment, 1301-1500, Bibliothèque nationale de France

Fig. 3. Illustration for Vincent of Beauvais's *Speculum Humanae Salvationis*, MS Add. 6447 (23v), parchment, at least second half of the 15th century, University of Cambridge

Phase 2:
Christ
crowned
with
crown of
thorns
and
mocked

Fig. 4. Illustration for Vincent of Beauvais's *Speculum Humanae Salvationis*, MS Latin 511 (21v), parchment, 1301-1500,

Fig. 5. Illustration for Vincent of Beauvais's *Speculum Humanae Salvationis*, MS Add. 6447 (25v),

	Bibliothèque nationale de France	parchment, at least second half of the 15 th century, University of Cambridge
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2. THE SUSPICIOUS GARMENT AND RESURRECTION OF THE BAPTIZED CHRIST

Nevertheless, the reason why Christ's garments, in all five aforementioned images, are not pigmented as scarlet or purple designated by the three Gospels but rather as white or plain, is hitherto unsolved. Both MS Latin 511 and MS Add. 6447 were painted with a dilute solution of carbon black or iron-gall ink, producing an effect of pale grey modelling which may to a certain extent explain the simplicity and whiteness of Christ's garment. And the follow-up question can be whether these manuscript images were taken in by Fra Angelico's *The Mocking of Christ* or not. According to information about country of origin, MS Latin 511 was fabricated in Alsace, whilst MS Add. 6447 originated from the North of Holland. Despite the geographical discrepancy, both manuscripts have an inheritance relationship in regards to the iconography of mocking. Thus, it is likely that Angelico's fresco may have referred to the coloring of Christ's garment that the above-mentioned manuscripts endowed. Apart from the pictorial resemblance that may account for the whiteness of Christ's garment, the trails of Christ in white, from the perspective of biblical illustration, run through the whole process of Christ's dying and rising. In Mark's illustration, Christ's transfiguration is described as "his raiment became shining, exceeding white as snow; so as no fuller on earth can white them"⁸, which in Matthew's Gospel is rewritten into an alternate version—"his face did shine as the sun, and his raiment was white as the light". It seems that in the Gospels there are only two statements that mention the white garment, in particular locating in the plot preceding Christ being mocked. Hence, biblical sources beyond the Gospels should be examined as well. When the Gospel of Matthew talks about Christ's

⁸ See *The Holy Bible, containing the Old Testament and the new: newly translated out of the original tongues, and with the former translations diligently compared and revised. By His Majesties Special Command. Appointed to be Read in Churches.* London: John Baskett and the Assigns of Henry Hills, deceas'd, 1728, Chap. xiv-3.

second-time suffering of being mocked, it is described as “they stripped him, and put on him a scarlet robe”⁹. The ritual of baptismal practice for early Christianity involved the stripping off of one’s clothes prior to immersion and then dressing again with a white garment, which denoted the ritual significance of absterging the sins and coming to a new life by means of re-clothing in white¹⁰. According to Theodore of Mopsuestia the Bishop, “since you came up from Baptism, you are clad in a vestment that is all radiant. This is the sign of that shining world...to which you have already come by means of symbols. When indeed you receive the resurrection in full reality and are clothed with immortality and incorruptibility, you will have no further need of such garments.”¹¹In Matthew’s narration, Christ, stripped and naked, is for the sake of mockery rendered a scarlet robe, which is then taken off and replaced by his own raiment. This metaphor of dressing and undressing bears resemblance to Christ’s dying and rising in the baptismal tradition, which by the Colossians is distinctly informed—“Do not lie to one another, seeing that you have put off the old nature with its practices and have put on the new nature.”¹² From stripping to redressing around the plot of mocking, a thorough remolding of Christ in a way analogous to alchemy is “in the making”, whose process will never finalize until “he that overcomes, the same shall be clothed in white raiment”¹³. Hence, the theological connotations that lie behind Christ’s getting his white raiment re-clothed are resurrection and formidable immortality. So far, the reason why Christ in Angelico’s *The Mocking of Christ* was depicted as wearing a white garment resurfaces, which further manifests the complexity of iconic narratives. As this story of Jesus’ baptism shares the same underlying logic of redressing with the

⁹ See *The Holy Bible, Containing the Old Testament and the New: Newly Translated Out of the Original Tongues, and with the Former Translations Diligently Compared and Revised. By His Majesties Special Command. Appointed to be Read in Churches.* London: John Baskett and the Assigns of Henry Hills, deceas'd, 1728, chap. xxvii-28.

¹⁰ Scroggs, Robin, and Kent I. Groff. “Baptism in Mark: Dying and Rising with Christ.” *Journal of Biblical Literature*, vol. 92, no. 4, 1973, p. 537.

¹¹ Jean Danielou, *The Bible and the Liturgy*, Notre Dame, Indiana, 1956, p. 49.

¹² Scroggs, Robin. “Paul and the Eschatological Woman.” *Journal of the American Academy of Religion*, vol. 40, no. 3, 1972, p. 291.

¹³ *The Holy Bible, containing the Old Testament and the new: newly translated out of the original tongues, and with the former translations diligently compared and revised. By His Majesties Special Command. Appointed to be Read in Churches.* London: John Baskett and the Assigns of Henry Hills, deceas'd, 1728, Chap. iii-5.

story of mocking, it is likely to have more biblical stories whose narrative structures or textual denotations may have been discreetly embedded in the story of mocking. The pictorial presentation could be an outcome of hybridizing both this narrative complexity and the varieties of interpretative possibilities.

3. HEROD'S BYCOCKET AND NARRATIVE INCLINATION FOR THE LUKE

In addition to Christ's outfit, other pictorial elements should be examined as well. The mocker, who stands on the right-hand side of Christ, is with his left hand holding a brown bycocket (or "chapeau a bec" in French), which has a wide brim rolled up at the back and heads out like a bird's beak in the front, a medieval hat popular for both genders, associated with heraldry and nobility and later with the burgeoning merchant class¹⁴. In the mid-20th century, Dr. Cohalan, the Bishop of Waterford and Lismore loaned four Benediction Copes and a set of High Mass vestments which were traditionally deemed as the gift of Henry VIII yet not conclusively confirmed to the National Museum of Ireland¹⁵. The Passion Cope, the third Benediction cope out of the four, represents on its third panel Christ before Herod, who coincidentally wears a hat of the bycocket type¹⁶. Amid four gospels are the stories about Herod mostly mentioned in the Luke: i.) Herod imprisons John (3:20); ii.) Herod is desirous to see Christ (9:7); iii.) Herod and his men mock the Christ (23:11)¹⁷. And the last event of Herod dealing with Christ is exactly the second phase of Christ's being mocked. As Angelico's *The Mocking of Christ* depicts the mocker as wearing a bycocket similarly showcased by Herod on the third panel of the Passion Cope from Waterford, it is likely that in the fresco this offender with bycocket may be an incarnated character of Herod and that the

¹⁴ Ruth A. Johnston. (2011). *All Things Medieval: An Encyclopedia of the Medieval World*. Santa Barbara, California: Greenwood. p. 330.

¹⁵ Catriona MacLeod. "Fifteenth Century Vestments in Waterford." *The Journal of the Royal Society of Antiquaries of Ireland*, vol. 82, no. 2, 1952, p. 85.

¹⁶ *Ibid.*, p. 93.

¹⁷ *The Holy Bible, containing the Old Testament and the new: newly translated out of the original tongues, and with the former translations diligently compared and revised. By His Majesties Special Command. Appointed to be Read in Churches*. London: John Baskett and the Assigns of Henry Hills, deceas'd, 1728, see Chap. iii-20, Chap. ix-7, and Chap xxiii-11 respectively.

image's main textual source shall be the Gospel of Luke.

4. DISEMBODIED HANDS ACCORDING TO AQUINAS' REALISM AND

INTENTIO

Beside the thorny crown, blindfold and garment as well as the mocker's bycock, those commander-like hands are very noticeable in the fresco. Apart from the left hand holding the bycock, the other four hands are normally interpreted as the mocker's right hands, though they are multi-located. Fra Angelico, in his early 20s, joined the Observant Dominican community of San Domenico in Fiesole above Florence with his brother as illustrators and miniaturists¹⁸. According to William Hood's *Fra Angelico at San Marco*, Angelico could be understood as a principal propagandist whose art could be placed in a vast social and ideological context of the Observant Movement in the 15th century Florence¹⁹. The doctrinal tradition and its articulated beliefs in particular Thomism that constituted the mindset of the observant Dominican reform are motives hidden behind Angelico's paintings. When Angelico died in early spring 1455, he was canonized as "the Angelic Painter" in parallel to Thomas Aquinas "the Angelic Teacher", which to a certain extent manifested his theological preference as a thorough Thomist²⁰. Angelico's aesthetics is deeply affected by his strong faith in Thomist worldview. Thomas Aquinas is an author renowned for considerable indirect knowledge of Platonic thoughts, which can be learned from his evaluation of the Platonic approach that the way of Platonist's speaking conforms to the "abstract" principle separating from matter ontologically, in the prologue of his commentary on pseudo-Dionysius's *De divinis nominibus*²¹. The Platonists insist that there's always a first principle, namely the essence of goodness or oneness, from which all other things are derived. Aquinas, unlike some other medieval philosophers who endorsed Aristotle's rebuttals in view of corporality that "Homo generat hominem: the begetter suffices for the coming-to-be of

¹⁸ Fisher, Anthony. "A New Interpretation of Fra Angelico." *New Blackfriars*, vol. 75, no. 882, 1994, p. 255.

¹⁹ *Ibid.*, p. 257.

²⁰ *Ibid.*, p. 261.

²¹ Jan A. Aertsen, editor. "The 'Platonist' Thomas Aquinas." *The Cambridge History of Medieval Philosophy*, by Jel Biard, 1st ed., Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 2010, p. 82.

things”, but rather, opposed the conception of the “Idea” being taken as a form of natural things detached from its subordinates. In *Summa Theologia*, Aquinas proposed that there must exist in the divine mind a form to the likeness of which the world was consisted, thus leading to the birth of the notion of an *Idea*²². Therefore, those disembodied “hands” or more strictly defined “palms”, in Angelico’s fresco, point to the existence of an abstract and universal idea of “slap”, while other detailed features such as the personalized faces that overflow the aims of expressing the most irreducible and supreme idea are deliberately wiped off. Aquinas conceived “truth” as having to be acquired and expressed by judging whether a thing corresponds to the form which it apprehends about that thing, rather than by knowing of a thing “what a thing is”²³. The concept of “slap” which may be further extended to “mock”, judging from Aquinas’ theological construction of truth, shall not be understood as the scene of one swinging a hand, but as the form through which the “slap” itself apprehends concerning it. Thus, the ontological being of “slap”—those detached hands in iconographical sense, has a total priority over subjectively construed statements about being—specific and individualized action of “slap”, which are of necessity always distant from being itself.

According to Aquinas’s commentary on Aristotle’s *De anima*, “Every cognition is produced by the cognized thing’s somehow being in the one cognizing—namely, in virtue of a likeness. For what is actually cognizing is the very thing actually cognized”²⁴, which incarnates his commitment to two claims: i) A likeness of Object (abbreviated as O) in Subject (abbreviated as S) can bring about S’s cognition of O. ii) In some sense, O must be in S.²⁵ Therefore, in virtue of a likeness of O (abbreviated as L(O)), O is represented by a species that makes S cognize O. And species in a broader sense denotes the form. For Aquinas, “An intelligible likeness, through which something is

²² Jan A. Aertsen, editor. “The ‘Platonist’ Thomas Aquinas.” *The Cambridge History of Medieval Philosophy*, by Jöel Biard, 1st ed., Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 2010, p. 84.

²³ Callum David Scott, “Saint Thomas Aquinas’ ontological epistemology as clarified realism: The relating of subject to object for ontological knowledge.” *South African Journal of Philosophy*, vol. 35, no. 3, 2016, p. 253.

²⁴ Thomas Aquinas, *A Commentary on Aristotle’s De anima*, Robert Pasnau trans., New Haven & London: Yale University Press, 1999, p. 199.

²⁵ Robert Pasnau, *Theories of Cognition in the Later Middle Ages*, Cambridge University Press, 1997, p. 86.

intellectively cognized as regards its substance, must be of the same species or rather must be its species”.²⁶ Hence intelligible likeness cannot be counted as belonging to the same species as the represented O, but rather, it is exactly the species of the O it represents. Intelligible likeness or species is what S cognizes in virtue of a likeness to O, whilst O as a synthesis of form and material, exists outside the S. Therefore, in face of Angelico’s *The Mocking of Christ*, cognition can be brought about through a likeness of the cognized mocking hands in the audience, as the hands cognized must in some way be in the audience, not of trivial or accidental features such as hand shape or gestures in detail. Aquinas proposed that the cognitive subject does not entail the accidental quality of its object, as in his *Quaestiones Disputatae de Veritate*, “Ad tertium dicendum quod inter cognoscens et cognitum non exigitur similitudo quae est secundum convenientiam in natura, sed secundum representationem tantum [...]”.²⁷ Thereby, the cognitive agent receives the species or forms in terms of representation *intentionally*, without taking on the all-embracing features of the cognized, which means that cognition needs no resemblance of whatever forms in natural sense. In Angelico’s fresco, offenders’ hands are depicted as disembodied, so as to lead audience as planned to cognize the attributes of Christ being mocked with slaps, by means of the likeness in terms of mockery represented by symbolic hands, rather than through an omnipotent demonstration of naturalistic hands and their affiliated body parts. No matter how many accidental features such as hand sizes, shapes as well as their associated skins etc. are added into the representation, they will never manage to dig up a particular person who really slapped Jesus in the face at that very historical moment. In fact, for a cognitive subject, the matter enlisted to describe an individual object regardless of its extent of detailedness can never equate with the object itself, unless the subject has a correct causal relationship with the object.

If taking a step back from the above inquiry into the participants (S, L(O), etc.) involved

²⁶ *Ibid.*, p. 87.

²⁷ Santi Thomae de Aquino, *Quaestiones Disputatae de Veritate, Volumen II. FASC. 1 QQ. 8-12*, Romae ad Sanctae Sabinae, 1970, p. 256.

in the process of cognition, the qualitative and causal analysis of cognition is yet to be examined. According to Aquinas, “A thing’s immateriality is the reason why it is cognizant, and the manner of its cognition occurs in keeping with the manner of its immateriality.”²⁸ Thus, the immaterial existence is closely connected with intentional reception of forms, and cognition requires a capacity that can fully receive forms *intentionally*. And the key features of things that are truly cognitive are to bear a great amount of information *intentionally* instead of materially. Things that are incorporeal and immaterial are more open to information, which in Aquina’s words “a kind of infinity” in regards to their reception of forms. Those reductionistic hands that erase individual traits and Aquinas’ *materia signata* depicted by Angelico’s fresco are very much immaterial and propose an infinity in receiving forms, nevertheless, they are, like air or water, not deemed as having the capacity of cognition, owing to a lack of “some kind of direction to an end.”²⁹ The cognitive is defined to be *anything that has appetites or desires*.³⁰ And it is not only a single appetite directed towards a single fixed end, but also multiple desires for the various things that predominate the cognitive agents, which is what Aquinas calls the “multiform” appetite. Only we humans, beside God and angels, have such multiform desires. Thus, we are among the Chosen Ones that are able to cognize something intentionally. According to the aforementioned endogenous principle of epistemic subject, we the cognitive agent, for the sake of multiple ends, projects multiform appetites to make of things. Thus, those disembodied hands may not just connote a sole discourtesy inundated with mockers’ cruelty, but open up to mental images forwarded by the cognitive subjects who deploy their sensory sense to help ration understand the object realistically, and directs to a different end via multiform appetites. The meaning of those hands with five fingers tightly jointed with each other, in another sense, may in form resemble one of the “folded hands”, with which Christians devoutly pray to God, just as vassals promise fidelity to their ‘feudal lords’³¹,

²⁸ Robert Pasnau, *Theories of Cognition in the Later Middle Ages*, Cambridge University Press, 1997, p. 50.

²⁹ *Ibid.*, p. 57.

³⁰ *Ibid.*, p. 58.

³¹ Edward Schillebeeckx, *The Church with a Human Face: A New and Expanded Theology of Ministry*, New York: Crossroad, 1985, p. 164.

probably arousing a cognitive ambiguity in audience (Fig. 6 & Fig. 7).

<p>Fig. 6. Fra Angelico, <i>the Upper Right Hand</i>, from <i>The Mocking of Christ, with the Virgin and Saint Dominic</i>, fresco, c. 1439-1443, Cell 7, Convent of San Marco, Florence.</p>	<p>Fig. 7. Albrecht Dürer, <i>Praying Hands</i>, Brush, gray and white ink, gray wash, on blue prepared paper, 1508, Albertina museum in Vienna, Austria.</p>

Thus, this divergent directivity of connotation points to Angelico’s distinctive artistic quality of *Dissemblance* constituted by a mere visual and colored intensity whose instrumental nature is to indicate an invisible image beyond the “figurative” aspect³². When we pay attention to the particular *Intentio* of those hands, between the affront and devout praying, we come to a zone where the depicted are “nonfigurative”, or relatively disfigured, or “situated between two or even several iconic categories”—a specific understanding of *Figura* by Fra Angelico³³. The concept of *Figura* predominated the history of formulations about the Eucharist that induced the miracle of conjunction between *figura* and *res* in rituals³⁴, wherein *figura* may bear no resemblance to the aspect. According to Saint Augustine’s *De doctrina christiana*, signs can with their referents, the objects signified, have dissemblance that goes beyond the aspect, and leaves a sensory impression “*ex se*” on the audience³⁵. Hence, from Angelico’s *The Mocking of Christ*, we may notice a hand locating on Christ’s right shoulder and

³² Georges Didi-Huberman, *Fra Angelico: Dissemblance & Figuration*, Trans. Jane Marie Todd. Chicago and London: University of Chicago Press, 1995, p. 10.

³³ *Ibid.*, p. 27.

³⁴ *Ibid.*, p. 35.

³⁵ Saint Augustine, *De doctrina christiana* 2.1.1.

hanging down, which, except for the informed biblical significance of humiliation, may also resemble a gesture of mildness and tenderness. From Gospel According to Luke, at the third phase of Christ being mocked, there are two other thieves suffering the crucifixion with him, who is asked by one of them whether he is able to save them. And Christ replies that “To day shall you be with me in paradise”³⁶. The aforementioned suspicious hand which seems to grow out of Christ’s sleeve, is now endowed with a sublime notion of fraternity and benevolence, which may acquire alongside the meaning of brutality another significance—Christ’s mercy.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This article deploys a syncretic vision of both image and text. After comparing different biblical sources, the similarities and discrepancies between Angelico’s pictorial presentation and biblical guidance lead to a close scrutiny of a sequence of images from two manuscripts of *Speculum Humanae Salvationis* which share similar attributes with Angelico’s. This inter-pictorial comparison arrives at a conclusion that Angelico’s fresco might have synthesized different phases of Christ being mocked. And Christ’s white garment illustrated by the fresco can be deemed as paying a tribute to the contemporaneous pictorial practice with ink pigment, as well as attempting to recur Christ’s glorious resurrection through making the act of redressing analogous to Christ’s rising in baptismal practices, which further complicates the circumstances of Angelico’s sources. Moreover, Christ’s mocker with bycock is suspected to be the established image of Herod, which suggests the probability that Angelico may have used the Gospel of Luke as his main source text. Additionally, those disembodied hands that have made an unprecedented acquaintance with art history become the pivotal objects in the last section of analysis. Thomas Aquinas’s critical approach towards platonic idea accounts for the reason why those hands (palms) are solely represented—the hands (palms) intended for barbarity corresponds to the form which they are

³⁶ *The Holy Bible, containing the Old Testament and the new: newly translated out of the original tongues, and with the former translations diligently compared and revised. By His Majesties Special Command. Appointed to be Read in Churches.* London: John Baskett and the Assigns of Henry Hills, deceas'd, 1728, see chap. xxiii-39.

apprehended as “slap” ontologically, other than defending for a slap “what a slap is”. According to Aquinas’ epistemic theories on “intentionality”, a likeness of those off-body hands can bring about audience’s cognition of the hands, which are received by cognitive agents who *intentionally* understand them out of multiform appetites. Thus those hands, though separate from bodies, are somehow depicted as refined and elegant: its surface meaning of frivolity may have another side—in light of Angelico’s practice of dissemblance and his unique understanding of *Figura*—some hands may be of those devout prayers, whilst the pendent one as described in Luke that Christ promises the thief to be with him in paradise can be canonized as that of Christ, merciful and benevolent.

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